

NEWSERA - Citizen Science as the
new paradigm for Science
Communication

Deliverable 8.1

H- Requirement No. 1

Revision: v1.2

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Concerned work package leader: Science for Change

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CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Cl: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

SUMMARY

NEWSERA is a project funded under the topic SwafS-19-2018-2019-2020-Taking stock and re-examining the role of science communication. For achieving their goals NEWSERA focuses on four target audiences, which correspond to the stakeholders represented by the **quadruple helix model - civil society, industry and companies, the scientific community, and the policy makers**. NEWSERA takes specially into account the citizen science practitioners, science communicators and data journalists according to the aim of implementing **Citizen Science Communication** and **Citizen Science Journalism** concepts. NEWSERA is going to use co-creation tools and gather the contributions and co-design solutions proposed by whole quadruple helix stakeholders throughout #CitSciComm Labs.

This document outlines the **ethical aspects with respect to the participation of humans in all project actions**. Particularly, **procedures and criteria to identify and recruit participants** according to ethical principles within national and European legislation are submitted.

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1. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CitSciComm	Citizen Science Communication
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H	Humans
IBERCIVIS	Fundación IberoCivis
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
UNIPD	Università degli Studi di Padova

Table 1: Acronyms used in deliverable D8.1 H - - Requirement No. 1

2. Introduction

Citizen science (CS) initiatives are changing the paradigm of science communication (SC). Launching a citizen science project requires the creation of a **complex ecosystem**, in which the **participation of quadruple helix stakeholders** (interdisciplinary career scientists; the public sector; industry, businesses and SMEs; NGOs, CSOs and society at large) is usually **a must**. This poses a challenge in terms of science communication due to: 1) the wide variety of specific science communication tools and strategies to be used for each target group, including digital, traditional and face to face actions to increase participation, and 2) the required continuous feedback to each stakeholder group to maintain the engagement throughout project execution, and to involve all stakeholders in all phases of research. Interdisciplinarity, another intrinsic characteristic of citizen science projects, is also a challenge, and communication is key between the different science disciplines involved to increase acceptance and mutual understanding. Science journalists also play a key role to overcome the current barriers that limit the further uptake of citizen science initiatives, so as to mainstream citizen science projects and results, increase trust among the whole range of stakeholders, and promote its support by the public sector, industry, the scientific community and society at large. They can help to increase the quality of citizen science projects and, at the same time, benefit from innovative approaches in science communication closer to society.

Deliverable D8.1 responds to the **Requirement No. 1 - Humans**, described in Section 5. Ethics and Security of the NEWSERA of the Grant Agreement (GA) p.38. These are relevant aspects of the project for this requirement:

- The procedures and criteria used to identify/recruit research participants will be based on the engagement of the **quadruple helix of stakeholders** model (public authorities, industry and SMEs, academia and citizens) following an **equity criteria**.
- Participants in NEWSERA and citizen science projects are researchers or, in many cases, citizen scientists. Therefore mutual learning and co-creation of knowledge are key for understanding the development of the project.

Like all EU countries, **the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** - Regulation (EU) 2016/679 applies on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

All project personnel will be trained in the importance of confidentiality of individual records and required to sign a confidentiality agreement.

2.1. Relation between D7.1, D7.2, D8.1, D8.2 and D8.3

NEWSERA is a citizen science communication project aiming to involve a quadruple helix of stakeholders (including citizens, NGO's, industries, local & regional authorities, and communication experts, amongst others), at local,

national and international levels during three years. Therefore, it will involve a high level of human participants, using different methodologies and tools for their involvement and participation in co-researching. Thus, ethical considerations and guidelines framing this wide participation is crucial and needed.

This deliverable is framed within WP8 - Ethics Requirements. As outlined in section 5.1 of the Grant Agreement (part B, p. 79), NEWSERA has been given conditional ethics clearance, and three issues have been identified:

- **Requirement N° 1** - Procedures and criteria used to identify research participants.
- **Requirement N° 2** - Data Protection Officer (DPO) and detailed personal data protection policy.
- **Requirement N° 3** - Templates of the informed consent.

These Requirements respectively correspond to deliverables D8.1, D8.2 and D8.3. and its contents are summarized below:

D8.1 : H - Requirement No. 1:

- The procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants.
- Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans must be obtained and kept on file.

D8.2 : POPD - Requirement No. 2:

- The host institution must confirm that it has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research. For host institutions not required to appoint a DPO under the GDPR, a detailed data protection policy for the project must be kept on file.

D8.3 : H - POPD - Requirement No. 3:

- The informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans.
- Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants).
- For children involved in the research, details on how their assent (as a first step in their recruitment) and the consent of the legal representatives (as a second step in the children's recruitment) will be acquired.

On the other hand, **WP7- Ethics and Data Protection** (GA, p.35) seeks to:

- Assess the ethical aspects associated to citizen science research and science communication activities involving data collection from/with citizens and other stakeholders.
- Design the Data Management Plan to allow for FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) data collection and storage.
- Guarantee Data Protection aspects and define the procedures to identify, recruit and engage research participants.

WP7 includes two deliverables:

D7.1 Data Management Plan:

- The Data Management Plan will ensure that all generated data is FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable).

D7.2 Report on ethics aspects as a cross-cutting issue in NEWSERA actions:

- A report on the ethical aspects co-identified with citizen science participants will be developed, following the participatory governance approach through a co-creation process - including inclusiveness when engaging participants.

The figure below illustrates the relationship between the deliverables of WP7 and WP8:

Figure 1: Relationship between deliverables D8.1-D8.2-D8.3 & D7.1-D7.2.

NEWSERA
#CITSCI IS THE NEW #SCICOMM

3. The NEWSERA criteria to identify/recruit research participants

3.1. The NEWSERA methodology for stakeholder engagement

NEWSERA has created a methodology to **involve the quadruple helix of stakeholders into co-creation processes to exploring citizen science as the new paradigm for science communication**. In the figure below, the NEWSERA methodology is illustrated. Through a consultation of citizen science projects using diverse strategies, as benefitting from the new [EU-Citizen-Science platform](#), NEWSERA will create **5 #CitSciComm Labs**, one per each stakeholder (*society at large, policy makers, industry, career scientists and journalists*), which will result at the end in the **blueprints for co-designing innovative communication strategies** using citizen science as a science communication tool in an iterative cycle, as shown in the figure below. The methodology includes the identification, recruitment and engagement of citizen science project experienced-stakeholders and science communicators & data journalists into the process.

Figure 2: The NEWSERA methodology

As a first step for the NEWSERA methodology, an online survey on ‘Science Communication through citizen science’ has been sent out in June 2020 to main European citizen science institutions and organizations to make a screening of

projects to achieve the identification of the ones that will finally participate in NEWSERA. Besides, an online collaboration meeting between SwafS projects coordinators will help to recruit research participants. The project will also make good use of partner networks from the citizen science experience within the Consortium. Finally, a combined face-to-face and virtual approach will enable NEWSERA to create a reliable, replicable method to engage research participants and be able to generate valid and actionable data to guarantee a proper ethics and data co-creation process with participatory interventions, as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 3 illustrates the stakeholders, objectives and science communication tools to be tested and evaluated through the NEWSERA pilots. The tools are varied and entail a set of criteria to identify and recruit research participants - which are explained in the next section.

Figure 3: NEWSERA will create five Citizen Science Communication Labs to co-design, test and evaluate innovative communication tools addressed to citizen scientists, careers scientists, policy makers, industry and SMEs, and science journalists. The #CitSciComm Labs will also allow to define the new concepts of Citizen Science Communication and Citizen Science Journalism by exploring the common ground of Science Communication, Citizen Science and Data Journalism.

3.1 Research participants

Research participants are not the object of study of the NEWSERA project - they are considered **co-researchers**, since we are dealing with an inclusive citizen science communication project. The project aims to research on citizen science and science communication, so the research does not entail sensitive information related to health, political ideology, religion, etc. and does not require any biological samples from the participants.

Research participants and the main different strategies and tools that will be used for their engagement are summarized below:

Participants in the online survey:

To achieve participation in the survey the project has used different means:

- All NEWSERA consortium members used their citizen science networks to disseminate the survey.
- A campaign was carried out through the social networks of all partners, both institutional and personal.
- The survey was disseminated by contacting with members of different citizen science European networks and projects, among them: ECSA, EU-Citizen.Science, ECSITE network, Flemish CS network, Spanish RedIRIS mailing list, Citizen Science Observatory in Spain, JRC Ispra, Natural History Museum Brussels, PCST mailing list, Austrian CS network, Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Danish Citizen Science Network, as well as in many different projects in Portugal, Italy, Germany, UK, France or Sweden.

Those who voluntarily accessed the survey page were given all the relevant information to be able to carry out the survey with their consent and to be able to exercise all their rights in this respect. Complete details are included in Deliverable D8.3H - POPD - Requirement No. 3.

Participants in the #CitSciComm Labs:

At the time we are presenting this deliverable, the #CitSciComm Labs have not started yet. The emergence of COVID-19 delayed their celebration, and a plan for its re-design to ensure the health safety of all participants is taking place. To date, the information published about the Labs is contained on the website.

Figure 4: Information about the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs on the website. Available at: <https://newsera2020.eu/labs/>

Although the celebration of the Labs has been postponed from June to October 2020 (online or in combination with offline meetings if possible) - potential participants have already expressed their interest in participating.

Using the survey described above, respondents were asked to voluntarily provide a contact email, in case they wanted to be informed about the survey results and/or in case they were interested in participate in the #CitSciComm Labs. This was not a mandatory question and it was asked at the end of the survey (see image below).

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A portrait of Science Communication Strategies by Citizen Science projects

Resume later Exit and clear survey Question index -

83%

Thanks, contacts and availability

The questionnaire is almost over. Thank you very much for your time and effort in answering our questions. We would like to keep in touch with your project. This last group of questions concerns exactly the opportunity:

- to be informed and updated about the general outcome of the survey;
- to provide consent to further collaborate with the NEWSERA project and to have the opportunity to be invited to our Labs activities.

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- to provide consent to further collaborate with the NEWSERA project and to have the opportunity to be invited to our Labs activities.

* Would you like to be informed about the general outcomes of the survey?

Yes

No

* Would you consent to be contacted in the near future for an interview to tell us more about the communication strategies of your project?

Yes

No

* Would you be available to receive an invitation to participate in the co-creation Citizen Science Communication Labs?

Yes

No

Citizen Science Communication Labs are aimed at improving science communication strategies for Citizen Science projects proposing innovative ways to open up science and innovation to key stakeholders. A further aim is to improve relationships of trust in science communication. The labs will allow to co-design and take advantage of bottom-up, co-created communication strategies that arise from citizen science projects.

Yes

No

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* Could you please indicate the name of your project?

* Please, type below the e-mail address where you or another contact person can be reached

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[?](#)

An e-mail address that you, or somebody from your organization, check regularly. NEWSERA will write you only about the issues connected to the outcome of the survey you filled. In case of your availability, NEWSERA may contact you in the coming weeks for inviting you to be interviewed and/or to take part to Citizen Science Communication Labs

Previous Submit

Figure 5: Respondents to the survey can voluntarily provide their contact details for being interviewed and/or for participating in the Labs.

As shown in Figure 5, the information provided to survey respondents includes **the invitation to everyone interested in participate as a researcher or citizen scientist in the NEWSERA project**. Their contact details and informed consents were necessary to be added.

In the box below, the point referring to participation in the #CitSciComm Labs and/or interviews when respondents acceded to the survey has been highlighted.

A portrait of Science Communication Strategies by Citizen Science projects

Welcome! You just landed on the NEWSERA survey about science communication practices as performed by citizen science projects across the European Union and the UK. We are a European consortium funded by the H2020 programme, studying citizen science as a new form of science communication that can strengthen the link between science and society.

If you manage a citizen science project in any discipline area you are the expert we are looking for. We will ask some questions about your project, the way it involves citizens and it shares its results across society and within communities of practitioners. Completing the survey will give you the opportunity to participate, expenses covered, to our co-creation Labs together with science communication experts and journalists. The Labs will consist in small group meetings, aimed at better understanding and improving

Figure 6: Page of UNIPD to directly access to the survey. Available at: <https://websurvey.unipd.it/survey/index.php/816644?lang=en>

The entire corresponding text is as follows, highlighting in bold **the call for participating in the Labs.**

Welcome! You just landed on the NEWSERA survey about science communication practices as performed by citizen science projects across the European Union and the UK. We are a European consortium funded by the H2020 programme, studying citizen science as a new form of science communication that can strengthen the link between science and society.

If you manage a citizen science project in any discipline area you are the expert we are looking for. We will ask some questions about your project, the way it involves citizens and it shares its results across society and within communities of practitioners. **Completing the survey will give you the opportunity to participate, expenses covered, to our co-creation Labs together with science communication experts and journalists. The Labs will consist in small group meetings, aimed at better understanding and improving science communication through a mutual learning process.**

The questionnaire will take about 15 minutes to be filled in. You are free to leave the survey at any moment and to resume it later just by clicking on the button "Resume later" on the top left of the page.

The results of this survey will be published as aggregated statistical data and will be processed in accordance with art.13 of the 2016/679 European Regulation. Data will be stored and protected by the University of Padova in its servers. By clicking on the "NEXT" button, your consent to the processing of personal data is implied pursuant to art. 13 of the European Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR). If you complete

and submit the survey keep in mind that, since all personal data are regulated under the GDPR, you can exercise your rights according to this law. You can request the complete elimination of your data by emailing to ethics@ibercivis.es. For any further detail please have a look at NEWSERA Survey Privacy Notice or write an e-mail to info@newsera2020.eu.

Within the development of the Labs, participants will be requested to **interviews and/or recordings** for providing information on the topic (opinions, experiences, explanations, etc.).

3.2 Equitable selection of the sample

Special attention has been put in applying an **inclusive approach** (non discriminating in relation to different social realities, gender, age, socio-economic statuses, academic level, etc.) in all the **co-designed tasks** in order to make sure to overcome participatory barriers in science communication, in particular due to the COVID-19 crisis. It is important from all points of view that participants in the different participatory activities of NEWSERA constitute a representation of society that is as broad as possible.

On the one hand, this is achieved by adopting the quadruple helix model. But this is not enough. Factors such as: the size of companies, the geographical scope of citizen science projects, the different levels of government, among many others, must also be taken into account.

On the other hand, care will be taken to ensure that participation is balanced in terms of gender of the participants, and other factors such as different educational backgrounds and social realities - adapting the engagement tools to involve a broader participation in this regard.

Both the informed consent procedures implemented for participation and the corresponding templates/assent forms, as well as information sheets, provided within D8.3 H-POPD -Requirement No. 3, in language and terms intelligible to the participants.

4. The #CitSciComm Labs in the COVID-19 context

To tackle the effects of the COVID-19 crisis within NEWSERA, the Consortium has rediven #CitSciComm Labs to a more decentralized way, organising local Labs in Portugal, Italy and Spain as well as adding virtual activities to increase the cooperation among all the attendees and promote mutual learning.

This new scenario has a significant impact in ethics and data protection terms due to combine face-to-face meetings, virtual participation and the use of third parties platforms and its own data policy. As a citizen science communication project,

NEWSERA is going to gather all additions and identify their contributors guaranteeing the same rights independently of its way to do it.

The complexity to take into account ethics and data protection is itself the first outcome of NEWSERA project. Therefore, these outcomes will be included into several Blueprints with the hope this is going to allow guidance for other citizen science projects to manage data policy in their own projects, in a virtual context and with a co-design aim.

As affirmed in other deliverables, this document is understood as to be a living document, which is able to adapt to a new social and community needs and requirements, during the development of the same project.

5. Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities

Regarding Personal Data Protection, the Grant Agreement points out, that the corresponding partner must check if a declaration on compliance and/or authorisation is required under national law for collecting and processing personal data as described in the proposal. If yes, the declaration on compliance and/or authorisation will be kept on file. If not, the declaration on compliance or authorisation is required under the applicable national law, a statement from the designated Data Protection Officer that all personal data collection and processing will be carried out according to EU and national legislation will be kept on file.

Ibercivis Foundation, the partner responsible for the fulfillment of data protection requirements, has worked to collect opinions and approvals from ethics committees from the University of Zaragoza, the Government of Aragon and other entities committees. For now, these committees understand human participation as referring to human beings as the research object. Therefore, there is not a proper Ethics Committee in the University of Zaragoza or the Government of Aragon to fulfill this task. To fill in this gap we have advocated for the creation of such an overarching committee that can deal with the ethics aspects associated to citizen science projects. We hope this important issue could be covered by the Actions of the CSA in Citizen Science [EU-Citizen.Science](#), that started in January 2019, in which Ibercivis is participating. This task is under development.

In any case, following the principles outlined in the GA, there will be, among other things:

- No collection of data from a citizen without permission;
- Information will only be used for the purposes covered by agreement, and will not be retained except as required for these purposes;
- Information will not be made public or provided to third parties without explicit permission;

- Contractual and technical controls will be applied to prevent information becoming inadvertently available to third parties.

On the other side, the phase of data compilation with citizens has not started yet, meaning that the drafts of informed consent forms and other requirements have been created and presented under D8.1, D8.2 and D8.3, but not used yet. Ibercivis will take care of storing the forms used with the citizens participating in the different activities, both collected in person and through the project electronic tools, and once a proper Ethics Committee is identified or created, it will be contacted for Approval and thus the present deliverable updated.

Detailed information on the procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction, and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation has been submitted as deliverable D7.1 on Data Management Plan.